

Influence of unusual hand over handwriting

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ABSTRACT

Handwriting is a unique form of written expressions, shaped by individuals motor skill and is heavily dependent on mental and intellectual personality of an individual. This research explores variations in handwriting samples based on handedness and gender. This study examines 8 major individual characteristics such as hesitation marks, letter formation, connecting stroke, tremor, shading, baseline alignment, embellishment and spacing. Total 180 samples were collected for this study from 30 individuals (15 males and 15 females). 6 samples were collected from each individual that too 3 from right-hand and 3 from left-hand. The study's findings reveal that male writers exhibit slightly more variations in handwriting (51%) compared to female writers (49%), with greater discrepancies observed when writing with the non-dominant hand. Notably, hesitation marks and tremors were more prevalent in left-hand samples, suggesting that handedness plays a significant role in forensic handwriting analysis. Variations based on gender were very subtle the study underscores the importance of motor control and coordination in handwriting variations, offering valuable forensic insights into forgery detection.

KEYWORDS

Handwriting examination, forgery detection, individual characteristics, handedness

INTRODUCTION

Document is any written or printed paper that provide any type of information. Any printed or written document whose authenticity is questionable is known as questioned document. It can be any type of document such as passports, cheques, forged signatures, exams papers, counterfeit currency and many more. Questioned document examination is a special branch of forensic science that deals with collection, analysis, and comparison of documents to

identify authenticity and to detect forgery, alterations and disputed handwritings. Examination of questioned document is done by many techniques such as ink and paper analysis, detection of alterations such as addition, erasures etc. Examiners use standard samples as a reference to compare with the questioned samples^[18]. Handwriting is the written speech of an individual with unique characteristics. Handwriting is a motor skill and is heavily dependent on mental, emotional, physical and intellectual personality of an individual. It has some unique characteristics that cannot be replicated. The fundamental principles of handwriting are no two individuals can have same handwriting, no individual can write in same manner twice due to natural variations.^[30,31]

Handwriting characteristics are classified into two parts: Class characteristics and Individual characteristics. Class characteristics are common to a group of people. Examples of class characteristics are- size, slant, pen pressure, skill and line quality. Size of handwriting varies from person to person some individuals tend to write small letters or alphabets and some tend to write in way that it is being enlarged. Slant is the angle at which the letter is inclined it can be rightward slant, leftward slant or vertical. Pen pressure is the force applied on writing instrument while writing on paper.

Individual characteristics are unique to every individual. It includes hesitation marks, connecting stroke, starting and ending stroke, rhythm, tremors, and embellishment. Hesitation marks refer to uneven pen lifts and retracing of letters. Rhythm refers to consistency in writing letters that leads to even spacing and neatness. Connecting stroke refer to line that joins alphabets and words. Embellishment is the application of cursive handwriting on any written document and make it eye catcher.

Handwriting is influenced by both internal and external factors. Internal factors include health conditions, age and influence of drug whereas, external factors include posture, writing surface etc. In this study individuals are asked to write with both hands i.e. left and right hands. As we know that writing with non-dominant hand leads to the development of new features that are slightly different from the handwriting of dominant hand^[8]. In that case we find the similarities and differences in handwriting samples of both hands which gives us an insight about the case that the alteration is happened or not. Majority of the literate population is right-handed. The dominant hand is not the one preferred by the individual but is an expression of brain asymmetry. A minor but significant part of the population is left-handed with a handful of ambidextrous ones (who can use both hands efficiently). Natural handwriting is more of a reflex movement that has some unique features that are unintentional and are done subconsciously. Whereas, when non dominant hand is used there are very drastic and visible changes in the handwriting characteristics of the individual as the person is not habitual to it.^[2]

Forgery is altering someone signature or handwriting by the means of attempting fraud. It is of many types: free-hand forgery, simulating forgery, traced forgery and copy-paste forgery. In free hand forgery the forger simply tries to copy any signature or handwriting in its own handwriting without actually making it similar to the genuine one. Traced forgery is where the forger placing a sheet of paper onto the genuine signature and traces it with any writing instrument. Simulating forgery is defined where the forger firstly practices or learn to exactly

make a replica of any signature or handwriting and after weeks of practicing it turns out exactly like a genuine signature. It becomes very difficult for handwriting analyst to differentiate between fraud and genuine signature. Copy-paste forgery refers to destroying the actual content and on its place paste a fraud one.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Total 180 samples were collected for this study from 30 individuals. Out of which 15 were male and 15 were female. Selected candidates were asked to give 6 samples, 3 from right-hand and 3 from left-hand. All the collected samples were distributed into 4 categories as Right-hand samples of female, left hand sample of female and right-hand sample of male, right hand sample of male. After examining all the samples an average percentage was calculated to compare the variations in handwriting among male and female samples. Handwriting samples were collected on A4 sheet, a standard sample and a ball point pen was also provided to the individuals . Values were assigned to characteristics based on most relevant, moderate and not significant.

Inclusion criteria selected for this research is as follow:

1. Individuals with age group 18-25 years
2. Individuals with right as their dominant hand.
3. Individuals without any neurological disorder.

Exclusion criteria selected for the same was:

1. Ambidextrous individuals will be excluded from this study.
2. Individuals with neurological disorders.

Handwriting characteristics were examined based on three variables.

Table 1: Value chart for all characteristics except letter formation

Most Significant	Moderate	Not Significant
3	2	1

Table 2: Value chart for letter formation

Conventional	1
Non-Conventional	2

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1: Average % variation among right-hand handwriting

Most prominently seen characteristics in this pie-chart are connecting stroke and spacing and least but noticeable features are shading, tremor, hesitation marks and letter formation.

Fig.2: Average % variation among left-hand female handwriting

- Hesitation marks and spacing are most prominent features with average 17% each.
- Shading, Letter formation and embellishment show noticeable but less dominant and less frequent feature with average 9%, 7% and 6%.

Fig.3: Variation in right-hand handwriting of male

Most commonly seen features in right-hand handwriting of male are spacing and baseline alignment. Connecting Stroke show moderate variation with average of 15% whereas, very less dominant features are shading, embellishment and hesitation marks.

Fig.4: Average variation in left-hand male handwriting

Most commonly seen handwriting variations in left-hand samples of males were Hesitation marks and tremors with average percentage of 17% and 16%. Baseline alignment, spacing and connecting stroke show moderate variations with average percentage 15%, 15% and 13%. Shading, letter formation and embellishment are less dominant but noticeable features with average 10%, 8% and 6%.

Average percentage variation in handwriting of both genders

Fig.4: Average % variation in both gender

- This show that 49% of female handwriting samples show variation in handwriting when written with both dominant and non-dominant hand.
- 51% of male handwriting samples show variations when written with both dominant and non-dominant hand.
- More variation were seen based on handedness as compared to gender.

CONCLUSION

This study examines variations in handwriting based on handedness and gender focusing on characteristics such as embellishment, letter formation, hesitation marks, tremor, spacing, shading, baseline alignment and connecting stroke. Male writers show more variations in handwriting (51%) as compared to female writers (49%). Both genders show less variation in handwriting when they were told to write handwriting sample with their right-hands whereas, in case of left-hand more variations were seen mainly in characteristics such as hesitation marks and tremors. This study concludes that handedness plays crucial role in forensic examination of any forgery as non-dominant hand tend to show more and noticeable variations in handwriting. While gender-based variations were subtle males exhibit more variations in handwriting as compared to females. Overall. This research provides an insight on how handedness depends on motor control and coordination.

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